

Spatially Continuous Functional Expansion Tallies on Unstructured Meshes

Jacob S. Merson¹, Hunter Belanger^{2,*}, Parth Singh¹

¹Department of Mechanical, Aerospace, and Nuclear Engineering, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, 110 8th St., Troy, NY, USA;

²Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, Service d'Études des Réacteurs et de Mathématiques Appliquées, 91191, Gif-sur-Yvette, France

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803972

ABSTRACT

Functional expansion tallies (FETs) have become a popular method to generate tallies from Monte Carlo simulations which are spatially continuous, and can therefore facilitate multi-physics coupling with finite-element method (FEM) based solvers in other physics domains. There are, however, several drawbacks with traditional FETs, such as requiring a set of orthogonal basis functions defined on the geometric region of the tally. Another constraint is that at the intersection between two FET regions, the functional values will not, in general, be continuous. In this work, we propose a new type of FET which we call the Lagrange FET, that can be scored on a general unstructured mesh. In the Lagrange FET, continuity is guaranteed between elements of the mesh, and orthogonal basis functions are not required, permitting the use of standard FEM interpolation techniques. A simplified version of the Lagrange FET method which supports regular Cartesian meshes has been implemented in the Abeille Monte Carlo code, and has been demonstrated on a 1D slab reactor problem in addition to the C5G7 benchmark.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, Functional Expansion Tally, Unstructured Mesh

1. INTRODUCTION

Performing simulations in continuous energy with almost no geometric approximations, Monte Carlo codes are able to perform reference solutions to problems in the realm of reactor physics, radiation shielding, and fusion reactor analysis. They are able to provide unbiased estimates of quantities such as particle flux or the reaction rate within a user provided volume of phase space. One difficulty, however, is the reconstruction of such quantities over a large spatial domain where the sought observable may have strong gradients. In such a case, a very fine mesh may be required to capture the necessary details of the sought field. Refining the tally mesh is unfortunately a double edged sword, as a smaller cell for tallying means it will take longer to obtain estimates with a satisfactory statistical uncertainty across the field. Despite recent acceleration of unstructured mesh tallies on GPUs, [1], spatially resolved tallies remain a computational bottleneck. Functional Expansion Tallies (FETs) have become a popular tool in recent years to counter these problems, with codes such as OpenMC, Serpent, and RMC supporting different forms of FETs [2, 3, 4]. The basic premise behind FETs is to approximate the spatial shape of a sought field as a sum of orthogonal basis functions over a given geometric region. During transport, the coefficients for each orthogonal function can be estimated and a spatially continuous function approximating the field can be retrieved [5].

One challenge with the traditional FET formalism is that orthogonal basis functions are required for the geometric shape upon which the tally is being constructed [5]. In Monte Carlo codes which support FETs today, one is generally limited to Legendre polynomials as basis functions in rectilinear bins or

*hunter.belanger@cea.fr. This work was primarily carried out while the second (corresponding) author was still located at the 1st affiliation.

Zernike polynomials in a cylinder [5, 3, 4]. Another limitation of traditional FETs becomes apparent if one is to obtain a FET for a field in each cell of a rectilinear mesh. One will soon observe that the FET is not continuous across cells. This makes field coupling in the context of multi-physics applications particularly challenging, as needed fields such as energy deposition should be spatially continuous. While some work has examined FETs with non-orthogonal basis functions, the optimal choice of basis can be problem dependent, and this approach still does not permit the tally to be spatially continuous across a mesh [6].

To be able to perform coupled multi-physics simulations of nuclear reactors or fusion devices, one would like to obtain fields from Monte Carlo simulations which are spatially continuous on an unstructured mesh. These fields could then be sent to other physics solvers which are based on the finite element method. Unfortunately, the two aforementioned limitations of traditional FETs preclude the ability to generate such a field. In this paper, we propose a generalization of FETs which permits one to tally a spatially continuous field on an arbitrary unstructured mesh. In Sec. 2 we outline the theory behind FETs on an unstructured mesh and the basic implementation details in a Monte Carlo transport code. Section 3 demonstrates this new capability on a simple 1D slab geometry problem, and on the 2D C5G7 reactor physics benchmark. Final remarks and conclusions are provided in Sec. 4.

2. THEORY AND IMPLEMENTATION

Our goal in this study is to recover the average value of an observable, $\psi(\mathbf{x})$ (such as the flux), that is continuous over a domain of interest. The resulting field, $f(\mathbf{x})$, which is “tallied” in the simulation should minimize some error norm with respect to the stochastic observable $\psi(\mathbf{x})$.

In this work, we minimize the L_2 norm of the residual $R(\mathbf{x}) = f(\mathbf{x}) - \psi(\mathbf{x})$ by optimizing the coefficients of the target field $f(\mathbf{x})$ which is defined as an interpolating function

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{A=1}^n f_A N_A(\mathbf{x}), \quad (1)$$

where f_A is the coefficient corresponding to the shape function $N_A(\mathbf{x})$ and n is the number of nodes in the unstructured mesh. Finding the coefficients f_A first requires that

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial f_A} \int_V R(\mathbf{x})^2 d\mathbf{x} = \frac{\partial}{\partial f_A} \int_V (f(\mathbf{x}) - \psi(\mathbf{x}))^2 d\mathbf{x} = 0. \quad (2)$$

After expanding and applying Eq. (1) we get

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial f_A} \int_V \left[\sum_{A=1}^n (f_A N_A(\mathbf{x}))^2 - 2 \sum_{A=1}^n (f_A N_A(\mathbf{x})) \psi(\mathbf{x}) + \psi(\mathbf{x})^2 \right] d\mathbf{x} = 0, \quad (3)$$

which subsequently leads to

$$\sum_{B=1}^n f_B \int_V N_A(\mathbf{x}) N_B(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} = \int_V N_A(\mathbf{x}) \psi(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x}. \quad (4)$$

In the context of a discretization on an unstructured mesh, Eq. (4) can be split into the sum of integrals over non-overlapping elements. To see the utility of Eq. (4), it can be recast as a system of linear equations

$$\hat{\mathbf{M}} \mathbf{f} = \mathbf{b} \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$ is the nodal mass matrix, \mathbf{f} is the vector of coefficients to be solved for and \mathbf{b} is a vector of integrals that must be computed from information about the shape functions of the target field and the

value of the tally. In this work, we use Lagrange shape functions with local support which means the mass matrix will be sparse.

The mass matrix contains no information about the source field and can be computed exactly using numerical integration techniques. To compute the \mathbf{b} vector (right hand side of Eq. (4)), Monte Carlo integration with a collision estimator is used:

$$b_A = \int_V N_A(\mathbf{x})\psi(\mathbf{x})d\mathbf{x} = \sum_{e=1}^{n_{\text{elements}}} \int_{V_e} N_A(\mathbf{x})\psi(\mathbf{x})d\mathbf{x} \approx \sum_{e=1}^{n_{\text{elements}}} \frac{V_e}{n_{\text{samples}}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{samples}}} N_A(\mathbf{x}_i)\psi_{\text{est}}(\mathbf{x}_i), \quad (6)$$

where V_e is the element volume and $\psi_{\text{est}}(\mathbf{x}_i)$ is the Monte Carlo response estimator for the quantity ψ . As an example, if estimating the flux at collisions one would have $\psi_{\text{est}}(\mathbf{x}_i) = w/\Sigma_t(\mathbf{x}_i)$ where w is the particle's statistical weight and $\Sigma_t(\mathbf{x}_i)$ is the total macroscopic cross section at the collision location \mathbf{x}_i . It should be noted that while we have presented our example with the collision estimator, there is no inherent limitation to the method that would preclude the use of a track-length estimator. All that is required for a track-length estimator is that $N_A(\mathbf{x})\psi_{\text{est}}(\mathbf{x})$ be readily integrated along a flight path (which can be done analytically for linear elements).

In this work, we have made no assumption requiring orthogonal shape functions. The foundational work on FETs by Griesheimer indicates that non-orthogonal functions can be used, but opted to use orthogonal functions as they are easier to implement and to prove error estimates about [5]. If orthogonal shape functions were used, the mass matrix $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$ would become the identity matrix and no linear solve would be required to obtain \mathbf{f} .

Similar to other types of FETs, this method does have a minor runtime cost. This cost is associated with the evaluation and storage of the shape functions of all nodes in the element containing a sample. The total storage required is equal to the number of degrees of freedom in the tally to be recovered. The required inversion of $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$ to obtain \mathbf{f} is an added overhead with regard to traditional FETs with orthogonal basis functions. However, the linear system does not need to be solved during the Monte Carlo simulation, and can be done once at the end in post processing. Similar systems of equations are routinely handled for finite element problems with hundreds of millions of degrees of freedom and recently as high as 55.5 trillion degrees of freedom on leadership class supercomputers [7].

2.1. Mass Matrix and Shape Functions for Axis Aligned Linear Quadrilateral Elements

For quadrilateral elements we define the shape functions as the tensor product of the normalized parametric coordinates ξ and η . We define a base finite element in the domain $\eta \in [-1, 1] \times \xi \in [-1, 1]$. The base Lagrange shape functions are simply:

$$l_1(\xi) = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \xi) \quad l_2(\xi) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \xi). \quad (7)$$

Therefore, the bilinear shape functions are given as:

$$N_1(\xi, \eta) = l_1(\xi)l_1(\eta) \quad N_2(\xi, \eta) = l_2(\xi)l_1(\eta) \quad N_3(\xi, \eta) = l_2(\xi)l_2(\eta) \quad N_4(\xi, \eta) = l_1(\xi)l_2(\eta). \quad (8)$$

We also, make use of the isoparametric mapping as follows:

$$x = \sum_{A=1}^4 N_A(\xi, \eta)x_A \quad y = \sum_{A=1}^4 N_A(\xi, \eta)y_A. \quad (9)$$

For a uniform grid, we can assume that $x_l \equiv x_1 = x_4$, $x_r \equiv x_2 = x_3$, $y_b \equiv y_1 = y_2$, $y_t \equiv y_3 = y_4$, where the subscript denotes the node number starting at the bottom left and numbering in a counter clockwise

fashion around the quadrilateral element. This lets us invert the mapping as:

$$\xi = \frac{x_l + x_r - 2x}{x_l - x_r} \quad \eta = \frac{y_b + y_t - 2y}{y_b - y_t}, \quad (10)$$

where, x_l is the x coordinate of the left edge of the element, x_r is the x coordinate of the right edge, y_b is the y coordinate of the bottom edge and y_t is the y coordinate of the top edge. And, we can define the Jacobian needed for integral mapping as

$$J = \frac{1}{4}(x_r - x_l)(y_t - y_b) = \frac{V_e}{4}. \quad (11)$$

This will give the elemental mass matrix contribution

$$\hat{\mathbf{M}}^e = \frac{V_e}{36} \begin{bmatrix} 4 & 2 & 1 & 2 \\ 2 & 4 & 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 2 & 4 & 2 \\ 2 & 1 & 2 & 4 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

The construction of the global mass matrix is defined as $\hat{\mathbf{M}} = \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{n_{\text{elements}}} \hat{\mathbf{M}}^e$ where $\mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{n_{\text{elements}}}$ is the finite element assembly operator that sums the nodal contributions of each element into the appropriate location in the global matrix through a mapping between the local degrees of freedom to the global equation numbers [8].

2.2. Implementation

The proposed methodology of Lagrange FETs has been implemented in the *Abeille* Monte Carlo code using the collision estimator on 2D regular Cartesian meshes [9]. Within a mesh element, the number of coefficients of the Lagrange FET will depend on the order of the shape functions and the type of the mesh element. When a particle has a collision inside a mesh element, the particle's contribution to the estimate of the right hand side of Eq. (5) is given by Eq. (6).

For convenience of shape function evaluation and extensibility to higher order shape functions, the particle position is converted to a parametric coordinate within the element that is defined by Eq. (10). The particle's contribution will be added to all the nodes in that element. In the estimation of b_A , the required shape function N_A will be the shape function that has a unit value at the node A in that element.

It should be noted that independent particle collisions in adjacent elements which share nodes will both lead to statistical contributions to the shared nodes. After completion of the simulation, the column matrix \mathbf{b} that is filled with the precalculated contributions of b_A can now be used for solving the linear set of equations as indicated in Eq. (5), thus obtaining all f_A . Subsequently, the flux (or any other quantity) at any desired point can successfully be recovered using Eq. (1).

Over the course of the simulation, the variance is also calculated for all right-hand side vector components b_A . The fact that the flux is obtained through solving a linear system of equations means that proper uncertainty propagation rules must be followed to retrieve the uncertainty at any position in the field. To evaluate the uncertainty on f_A , the covariance matrix of \mathbf{f} is calculated as

$$\text{cov}(\sigma_{f,n}^2) = \hat{\mathbf{M}}^{-1} \text{diag}(\sigma_{b,n}^2) (\hat{\mathbf{M}}^{-1})^T, \quad (13)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{M}}^{-1}$ is the inverse of the global mass matrix, $(\hat{\mathbf{M}}^{-1})^T$ is the transpose of the inverse of the former, and $\text{diag}(\sigma_{b,n}^2)$ is the $N_{\text{node}} \times N_{\text{node}}$ diagonal matrix, where the diagonal elements are the variances, $\sigma_{b,n}^2$, for coefficient b_n at node n , computed during the simulation [10]. The variance on the recovered field at a position can be calculated in a similar manner to that proposed in Griesheimer's work [5]:

$$\sigma_f^2(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{A=1}^{N_{\text{nodes}}} \sum_{B=1}^{N_{\text{nodes}}} \left(\text{cov}(\sigma_{f,n}^2)_{A,B} N_B(\mathbf{x}) N_A(\mathbf{x}) \right). \quad (14)$$

(a) Lagrange FET with 5 bins.

(b) Lagrange FET with 10 bins.

Figure 1. Flux in the slab with a regular mesh tally and a continuous Lagrange FET.

3. DEMONSTRATION PROBLEMS

The outlined methodology for continuous Lagrange FETs is demonstrated on an infinite slab problem and the 2D C5G7 benchmark. In both problems, the flux was obtained using the Lagrange FET with linear shape functions and was subsequently compared with a traditional Cartesian mesh tally; both types of tallies employed the collision estimator.

3.1. Infinite Slab

The infinite slab problem is a one-group system with a width of 1.540 64 cm. The slab's total, capture, and fission cross-sections are $\Sigma_t = 1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Sigma_c = 0. \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $\Sigma_f = 0.266667 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The differential scattering cross-section is $\partial\Sigma_s/\partial\mu = 1.466666(0.5 + 0.1818182645\mu)$, and the average number of neutrons released per fission is $\nu = 2.5$. The Monte Carlo simulation was performed with 10^6 particles with 50 inactive and 1000 active generations. The flux from the Lagrange FET was obtained on two different meshes: 5 and 10 bins spanning the length of the slab, corresponding to 6 and 11 nodes, respectively. Fig. 1 shows the flux obtained from the regular mesh tally and the continuous Lagrange FETs. The regular mesh tally used 50 bins. The Lagrange FET evaluated with 5 bins does quite well at approximating the cosine shape of the flux as shown in Fig. 1(a). The linearity in the Lagrange FET is due to the use of linear shape functions within each element. Refining the mesh to 10 bins, the Lagrange FET has excellent agreement with the traditional mesh tally, as seen in Fig. 1(b). Moreover, the flux obtained using the Lagrange FET is continuous across the domain. This confirms that the proposed methodology of the continuous Lagrange FET can successfully recover the flux, or any other quantity of interest.

3.2. C5G7

We have also applied the Lagrange FET method to a realistic LWR analysis problem: the 2D variant of the C5G7 multi-group benchmark. The Monte Carlo simulation was performed with 10^6 particles using 100 inactive and 3000 active generations. The Lagrange FET and regular mesh tallies were obtained from same simulation (i.e., using the exact same particle histories) and were scored on same 153×153 regular Cartesian mesh. Fig. 2(a) and (b) show a comparison of the volume integrated flux between the regular mesh tally and the Lagrange FET along the diagonal of the reactor in groups 1 and 7, respectively. Generally, the two estimates are in excellent agreement with one another. In group 7, the flux in the

Figure 2. Comparison of the volume integral of the flux between the regular mesh tally and the Lagrange FET in C5G7.

guide tube cells is slightly over-estimated by the Lagrange FET when compared to the regular mesh tally, though there is less than a 2.0% relative difference.

The volume integrated flux from the Lagrange FET in the thermal group is provided in Fig. 3a. This was compared with the regular mesh tally evaluated on the same spatial mesh. Fig. 3b shows the standard deviation of the volume integral of the Lagrange FET in group 7; the maximum standard deviation in the Lagrange FET is $1.8721 \cdot 10^{-6}$, while the maximum standard deviation in the regular mesh-tally is $5.3558 \cdot 10^{-7}$ near the corner of the reflective boundary. The relative difference (%) in the core and a magnified view of the relative difference within fuel assemblies are shown in Figures 3c and 3d, respectively. The relative difference within the fuel assemblies is higher than elsewhere in the core, and varies from -6.27 to 5.18% . These higher relative differences are driven by the steep gradients in the flux caused by the interfaces between materials. In this case, the flux gradient between the moderator and the fuel pin is very steep, leading to an “effective discontinuity”. Since the Lagrange FET formalism enforces that the field be continuous over the mesh, it can struggle to adequately capture such discontinuities which may occur at material boundaries. This is a case where it would be beneficial to have discontinuous interfaces between conformal meshes for each material region, allowing accurate modeling of these effective discontinuities. In the reflector region, where there are no material boundaries, the errors are well within one percent. The main exception to this is along the vacuum boundaries or at the far corner of the core, where there is very little neutron flux and the relative differences are dominated by the low statistics in that region of the problem.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have developed the theory to perform functional expansion tallies (FETs) on unstructured meshes, called Lagrange FETs. In this formalism, the resulting field is spatially continuous across the elements of the mesh. This therefore makes it trivial to perform field transfers between different physics solvers, as the energy deposition field is immediately in a state suitable for use in a finite element method based solver. Our approach does not require the use of orthogonal basis functions within elements of the mesh, and directly uses the Lagrange shape functions when scoring and to reconstruct the field within an element.

To demonstrate this new type of FET, we implemented the technique in the Abeille Monte Carlo transport

(a) Volume integral of the flux from the Lagrange FET.

(b) Standard deviation of Lagrange FET's volume integral.

(c) Relative difference in volume integral of the flux.

(d) Magnified view of (c) over the four fuel assemblies.

Figure 3. Volume integral of the flux and relative difference in group 7 of C5G7.

code for regular Cartesian meshes, and tested it on two multi-group problems: a one group slab problem and the 2D C5G7 benchmark. The Lagrange FET method was able to accurately reconstruct the flux within both problems, and gave a better estimate using fewer points for the slab geometry. While we only tested the method on regular Cartesian meshes, as an initial proof-of-concept, it is quite trivial (from a mathematics perspective) to implement this technique for general unstructured meshes, assuming one already has the infrastructure to efficiently perform operations on such meshes in the code base. While the method can struggle to capture discontinuities at material boundaries, due to the method forcing a continuous solution, one can use a different mesh for different material regions to counter this problem. Our tests also only considered linear elements, but the extension to quadratic or higher order elements is quite trivial.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was supported by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science FES and ASCR, under awards DE-AC52-0TNA27344 (FASTMath SciDAC Institute), DE-AC02-09CH11466 (StellFoundry: High-fidelity Digital Models for Fusion Pilot Plant Design and Computational Evaluation and Design of Actuators for Core-Edge Integration (CEDA)), and through a DOE ASCR SBIR entitled Geometry and Meshing Technologies to Support Fusion Energy System Simulations (DE-SC0024838).

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Hasan, C. W. Smith, M. S. Shephard, R. M. Churchill, G. J. Wilkie, P. K. Romano, P. C. Shriwise, and J. S. Merson. “GPU Acceleration of Monte Carlo Tallies on Unstructured Meshes in OpenMC with PUMI-Tally.” (2025). ArXiv:2504.19048.
- [2] P. K. Romano, N. E. Horelik, B. R. Herman, A. G. Nelson, B. Forget, and K. Smith. “OpenMC: A state-of-the-art Monte Carlo code for research and development.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 82**, p. 90–97 (2015).
- [3] B. Wendt, L. Kerby, A. Tumulak, and J. Leppänen. “Advancement of functional expansion capabilities: Implementation and optimization in Serpent 2.” *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **volume 334**, pp. 138–153 (2018). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0029549318305144>.
- [4] N. An, Q. Pan, X. Guo, S. Huang, and K. Wang. “A new functional expansion tallies (FET) method based on cutting track-length estimation in RMC code.” *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **volume 391**, p. 111736 (2022).
- [5] D. P. Griesheimer. *Functional Expansion Tallies for Monte Carlo Simulations*. PhD, The University of Michigan (2005).
- [6] Z. Han, B. Forget, and K. Smith. “Using Generalized Basis for Functional Expansion.” *Journal of Nuclear Engineering*, **volume 2(2)**, p. 161–167 (2021).
- [7] S. Henneking, S. Venkat, V. Dobrev, J. Camier, T. Kolev, M. Fernando, A.-A. Gabriel, and O. Ghattas. “Real-time Bayesian inference at extreme scale: A digital twin for tsunami early warning applied to the Cascadia subduction zone.” (2025). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2504.16344>. ArXiv:2504.16344 [cs].
- [8] T. J. R. Hughes. *The Finite Element Method: Linear Static and Dynamic Finite Element Analysis*. Dover, Mineola, NY (2000).
- [9] “Abeille Monte Carlo Code.” <https://github.com/HunterBelanger/abeille>.
- [10] M. Grabe. *Measurement Uncertainties in Science and Technology*. Springer (2005).